

Funded by the
European Union

EURL-PH-FWDB

EU Reference Laboratory for public health on food- and water- borne bacteria

Grant Agreement Number: 101244118

Project Title: EU Reference Laboratory in public health in the field
of food- and water-borne bacteria

Project Acronym: EURL-PH-FWDB

EU4Health Programme

Deliverable: D1.1 – Work plan – Year 1

STATENS
SERUM
INSTITUT

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

DOCUMENT OVERVIEW

Deliverable number	D1.1
Deliverable name	Work plan – Year 1
Work package number / name	WP1 / Coordination
Task number / name	T1.1 / Coordination of activities with network laboratories and ECDC
Due Date	M2 / 28 February 2026
Date of submission / version	24.02.2026 /v1
Dissemination level	Public
Authors	Egle Kudirkiene, Maren Lanzl, Linda Visser, Rosangela Tozzoli, Valeria Michelacci, Eva Møller Nielsen, Maaïke van den Beld, Stefano Morabito
Lead Beneficiary	Statens Serum Institute
Project website	
The deliverable agreed with ECDC	18.02.2026 Cecilia Jernberg, Taina Niskanen

1 LIST OF ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DG SANTE	Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EQA	External Quality Assessment
EU	European Union
EURL	EU Reference Laboratory
FWD-Net	The European Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses Network
GA	Grant Agreement
HaDEA	Health and Digital Executive Agency
ISS	Istituto Superiore di Sanità
MS	Milestone
MTA	Material Transfer Agreement
NA	not applicable
NFP	National Focal Point
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OCP	Operational Contact Point
PU	Public
RIVM	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu
RT-PCR	Reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SSI	Statens Serum Institute
SRM	Surveillance and Response Management system (ECDC)
STEC	Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	LIST OF ACRONYMS	3
2	INTRODUCTION	5
3	PROJECT ACTIVITIES IN 2026	6
3.1	WORK PACKAGE 1: COORDINATION	6
3.2	WORK PACKAGE 2: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION.....	8
3.3	WORK PACKAGE 3: SUPPORT TO NETWORK LABORATORIES	10
3.4	WORK PACKAGE 4: EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSESSMENT SCHEMES (EQAs)	12
3.5	WORK PACKAGE 5: SCIENTIFIC ADVICE AND TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE	14
3.6	WORK PACKAGE 6: TRAINING	16
4	PROGRESS REPORTING	21
5	DOCUMENT REVIEW / APPROVAL (THE COORDINATOR)	22

2 INTRODUCTION

In this report we present projects activities planned in 2026 corresponding to the agreed work plan under the Grant Agreement 101244118 for the EU Reference Laboratory for Public Health on food- and water-borne bacteria (EURL-PH-FWDB). This is the first out of seven Annual EURL work plans to be produced for Task 1.1 of Work Package 1 at M2, and M10, M22, M34, M46, M58 and M70, respectively.

The activities described in the work plan are aimed at supporting networking, addressing challenges in harmonising diagnostics, strengthening laboratory capacity, and improving outbreak preparedness in public health laboratories. The EURLs work is thus divided into six work packages addressing different areas of support:

- **Collaboration and networking (WPs 1-2)** focus on facilitating knowledge exchange among the network laboratories, evaluation of project activities, as well as coordinating activities and sharing information with all relevant stakeholders about the project’s plans and outcomes.
- **Support to network laboratories (WP 3)** in the form of reference diagnostics, protocols, reference materials, direct technical support and scientific advice on method implementation and optimisation and another needed laboratory guidance.
- **EQAs (WP 4)** ensure high diagnostic and typing accuracy, consistency, and comparability across network laboratories.
- **Scientific advice (WP 5)** providing laboratory expertise and scientific advice to European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and other stakeholders, e.g. in relation to outbreaks, risk assessments, laboratory methodology, molecular typing data management and sharing, and network surveys on specific topics.
- **Capacity building (WP 6)** delivers training programs to enhance laboratory capabilities and improve preparedness for cross-border health threats.

The six WPs consist of 16 tasks with their indicative nine milestones. The coordination of the WPs is distributed over the consortium partners. The execution of the work is performed by all consortium partners with a special focus depending on the five major target pathogens; SSI is first contact point for *Campylobacter* and *Listeria monocytogenes*, RIVM for *Salmonella* and *Shigella* and ISS for STEC. However, all consortium partners cover all organisms in their NRLs, meaning that each partner can replace the others or share the workload if necessary. Scientific advice or outbreak response requests (WP5) regarding *Yersinia* spp., *Vibrio* spp. or other food- and waterborne bacteria will be distributed over consortium partners *ad hoc*.

Figure 1. Work package (WP) and pathogen distribution among consortium partners in the EURL-PH-FWDB *Task numbers in italic correspond to the 13 tasks in the call text (EU4H-2024-DGA-MS-IBA-03).

3 PROJECT ACTIVITIES IN 2026

This section describes the EURL activities planned for 2026 in accordance with the Grant Agreement (GAP-101244118). The submission deadlines for all deliverables and milestones are listed in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively, and their implementation timeline is illustrated in the Gantt chart (Figure 2).

The descriptions below focus on the scope and content of the activities to be carried out in 2026. Deliverable and milestone identifiers are referenced where relevant, while detailed schedules are provided exclusively in the tables and the Gantt chart. Expected internal outcomes are described under each task.

All deliverables produced in 2026 will be prepared in accordance with the requirements set out in the Grant Agreement, including any conditions on content, approval, dissemination level and compliance with third-party rights, and will be agreed with ECDC where required prior to submission to HaDEA.

3.1 WORK PACKAGE 1: COORDINATION

Task T1.1 - *Coordination of activities with network laboratories and ECDC. Lead: SSI.*

SSI is responsible for coordinating all EURL-PH-FWDB activities. The project manager (PM), Egle Kudirkienė, started her role in January 2026. Overall EURL planning is undertaken by the coordination team, consisting of the PM and the technical WP leads (WP3–WP6), as well as by technical WP teams for WP3–WP6, composed of WP leads and additional personnel from each institute. Both, the coordination team and technical WP teams hold regular meetings to coordinate project activities. More detailed internal consortium coordination and decision-making are described in the Consortium Agreement, finalised at the end of January 2026. An EURL-PH-FWDB SharePoint site has been established and is used to organise and share work-related folders between consortium partners, supporting effective planning and execution of project activities.

Coordination of EURL activities with ECDC is ensured through regular and *ad hoc* meetings with ECDC contacts, including participation in FWD-Net meetings when invited. The first meeting with ECDC is scheduled for 11 February 2026. This meeting served as the first step in discussions and clarifications regarding the EURL work plan for Year 1 and procedures for collaboration between the EURLs and ECDC.

This draft EURL work plan (**D1.1**) was presented at the EURL kick-off meeting on 29 January (**MS2**), where HaDEA, DG SANTE and ECDC also gave presentations. EFSA, EURLs in food and feed, and WHO representatives participated as observers and were able to discuss. In total, 40 participants attended the meeting and the presentations were distributed to all participants by email on 6 February 2026.

To ensure coordination with network laboratories, the annual EURL work plan will be presented at an online information meeting for network laboratories on 19 March (**MS3**). HaDEA, DG SANTE and ECDC will be invited to participate and present at this meeting. All NFPs and OCPs will be invited based on the network laboratory contact lists obtained through the SRM system managed by ECDC (**MS1**). Three consortium representatives have been nominated and are awaiting access to the SRM system.

All meetings will be preceded by an agenda and followed by documented meeting outcomes, in line with the Grant Agreement. Regular coordination team meetings, management board meetings, WP team meetings and coordination meetings with ECDC are conducted and documented as internal milestones throughout the year (Q1–Q4, internal).

The EURL work plan for Year 2 will be developed considering the results of the first-year activities (**D1.2**).

Expected outcomes:

- EURL coordination structures (coordination team, WP teams and management board) are in place and operational (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- Consortium governance and decision-making processes are applied (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- Regular and *ad hoc* coordination with ECDC and network laboratories takes place (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- The Annual EURL work plan for Year 1 is implemented and used to inform adjustments to the work plan for Year 2 (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- Network laboratory contact information is available for coordination and communication activities (Q1, Internal).

Task T1.2 - Organisation of network meetings for network laboratories. Lead: SSI.

The first physical network meeting for network laboratories will be organised on 8–9 October 2026 in Copenhagen. The meeting agenda will include presentations on completed and planned EURL activities, as well as relevant technical and scientific topics. Network laboratories will have the opportunity to provide feedback and to exchange scientific and technical expertise.

At least one representative from each participating country will be invited (minimum 30 participants). Representatives from ECDC, DG SANTE and HaDEA will be invited to attend. Speakers from other Public Health EURLs, EURLs in food, feed and animal health, or experts from other relevant institutions or organisations may be invited when relevant.

Presentations and minutes from the meeting will be shared with network laboratories via the ECDC SharePoint site dedicated to the EURL-PH-FWDB and the laboratory network. The meeting agenda will be prepared and agreed with ECDC no later than one month before the meeting takes place and submitted in accordance with the Grant Agreement (**D1.8**). Following the meeting, a report containing the meeting minutes, presentations, participant list and evaluation results will be prepared and submitted as a separate deliverable (**D1.15**).

Expected outcomes:

- At least 30 participants from the network laboratories have access to one annual network meeting organised by the EURL (Q4, Internal).
- Network laboratories are provided with information on past and planned EURL activities through the network meeting (Q4, Internal).
- Presentations from the network meeting are made available to network laboratories (Q4, Internal).
- Outputs from the network meeting, including presentations and key discussion points, are available to ECDC and the project team (Q4, Internal).

Task T1.3 - Coordination with other EURLs or relevant initiatives. Lead: SSI.

The EURL participated in the first annual meeting of the EURLs Network in Public Health (EURL-PH Net) in Luxembourg on 22–23 May 2025 and plans to participate in the second meeting on 27–28 April 2026 in Stockholm. The EURL also participates regularly in monthly catch-up and topic-specific meetings of the EURL-PH Net organised by ECDC.

The EURL already has a close contact with most EURLs in food and feed and other relevant initiatives through related past and current consortium partners activities. Based on this, a contact list of relevant EURLs and other initiatives will be established to support coordination of activities (**MS4**).

Coordination with relevant EURLs in food/feed, WHO Collaborative centers, EFSA, PulseNet International and EUCAST is supported through their participation in annual EURL-PH-FWDB meetings for network laboratories and through EURL participation in their respective events. For example, EURL-PH-FWDB representatives will be available to participate in the annual meetings of the EURLs for specific food borne bacteria in the food sector, upon invitation. Representatives of relevant initiatives were invited to the EURL Kick-off meeting. Five representatives from EFSA, three from EURL *Salmonella*, two from EURL *Campylobacter*, one from EURL-AR, two from EURL *Listeria* and two from WHO CC for *Listeria* attended the meeting.

Expected outcomes:

- Coordination with other EURLs and relevant initiatives takes place through participation in relevant networks and meetings (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- Information exchange with EURLs in public health and in food/feed supports awareness of ongoing activities and alignment across initiatives (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- Contacts with relevant EURLs and international organisations are maintained to support collaboration and coordination activities (Q1–Q4, Internal).

3.2 WORK PACKAGE 2: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

Tasks T2.1-2 - Continuous communication with the network laboratories and relevant stakeholders and dissemination of EURL output of support activities. Lead: SSI.

Due to overlapping communication and dissemination channels, the below description applies to both Tasks T2.1 and T2.2.

To carry out the planned work, the EURL will interact directly with network laboratories and relevant project stakeholders through dedicated mailboxes and will disseminate project outputs through the ECDC SharePoint sites and the project website. For example:

- The EURL mailboxes will include a general mailbox and specific mailboxes used for communication with stakeholders on WP1 and WP2 tasks and for the distribution and organisation of work in technical work packages (WP3–WP6) (**MS5**).
- The ECDC SharePoint site dedicated to the EURL and the network laboratories will be used to share draft deliverables, SOPs and sensitive materials from EURL events (**MS6**).

A leaflet informing on the objectives and results of the project will be designed in accordance with Article 17 of the GA (**D2.1**). The leaflet will be shared with network laboratories and

relevant stakeholders by email and made available on the project website.

Project results will also be communicated to the Public and disseminated to the scientific community, industry stakeholders and policymakers through the project website, using language and formats appropriate to each target audience. In addition, LinkedIn will be used to share project-related information via social media. The EURL website will be developed as a subsite of the coordinating institute's website and will contain elements recommended by ECDC and required under Article 17 of the GA (**D2.2**). All project deliverables with a "Public" dissemination level will be published on the website as soon as possible following approval by HaDEA, in compliance with national accessibility and visibility requirements.

The first annual newsletter providing information on ongoing and upcoming activities will be produced in Q4 and shared via email and on the EURL website. In consultation with the network laboratories and ECDC, key EURL outputs based on anonymised and aggregated results will be presented to a wider international audience at relevant international scientific conferences and meetings.

To ensure consistent communication, the EURL will develop templates for letters, reports and presentations in line with EC guidelines and will establish an internal procedure for deliverable preparation, review, agreement with ECDC and submission to HaDEA. All communication and dissemination activities will be described in detail in the Communication and Dissemination plan (**D2.3**), which will also include relevant indicators for monitoring and evaluation of EURL activities across the technical work packages.

Expected outcomes:

- EURL communication channels with network laboratories and stakeholders are established and maintained, including mailboxes, secure share platforms and the project website (Q1-Q4, Internal)
- Project objectives, activities and results are communicated and disseminated to relevant audiences through appropriate channels, including the website, newsletters, social media and scientific meetings (Q1-Q4, Internal)
- Standardised templates and internal procedures support consistent EURL communication, reporting and deliverable preparation (Q1, Internal)

Task T2.3 - Evaluation of EURL activities. Lead: SSI.

The EURL will develop and apply a harmonised evaluation framework, including templates and objective evaluation criteria, to collect participants' feedback on network meetings (T1.2, WP1), EQAs (WP4) and training activities (WP6). Feedback will be collected as part of the respective activities and immediately following their completion.

In the first year, the EURL, in collaboration with ECDC, will develop additional specific action-level indicators to support evaluation of the overall impact of EURL activities through dedicated surveys conducted in the mid-term (**MS8**) and at the end of the project (**MS9**). Activity-specific evaluation criteria and additional indicators will be described in the Communication and Dissemination plan. These indicators will be used in designing a first-year survey (**MS7**) aimed to establish a baseline for assessing changes in laboratory capacity and capability at national and EU level over time. In addition, the survey will be used to identify national laboratories' needs for support.

Evaluation results will be analysed and presented at consortium meetings, progress meetings

with ECDC and the annual network meeting with network laboratories, and will be used to inform planning, prioritisation and continuous improvement of EURL activities.

Expected outcomes

- Harmonised evaluation survey templates and objective evaluation criteria available to support systematic collection of feedback across EURL activities (Q2, Internal)
- Additional specific action-level Indicators to measure positive changes in the network laboratories available (Q1, Internal)
- A baseline assessment of national laboratories' services and needs for support informs evaluation of changes in laboratory capacity and capability (Q4, Internal)
- Evaluation results support planning, prioritisation and reporting of EURL activities (Q3–Q4, Internal)

3.3 WORK PACKAGE 3: SUPPORT TO NETWORK LABORATORIES

Task T3.1 - *Provision of reference diagnostics and genotypic and phenotypic characterisation services for network laboratories in relation to Salmonella, STEC, Listeria, Campylobacter and Shigella, upon request. Lead: ISS.*

The EURL will provide reference services for the detection and characterisation of relevant pathogens, including WGS-based bioinformatic analysis, genotypic and phenotypic characterisation of isolates from challenging or atypical samples, and diagnostic assays involving complex matrices. Services will be delivered within defined turnaround times depending on the type of request.

ISS will coordinate this task, ensuring the availability of an annually updated, pathogen-specific inventory of reference services across partner institutes and harmonised procedures for service request submission, sample handling and result reporting. A legally compliant framework for sharing material and data will be applied, and a secure platform will be used for sharing sequence data.

All service requests will be registered and reviewed to identify emerging needs and to inform training activities (WP6) and dissemination of network-wide guidance (WP2). In parallel, the EURL will maintain and expand a curated repository of SOPs, laboratory protocols and guidance documents for pathogen detection and characterisation.

Expected outcomes:

- Network laboratories have access to reference diagnostic and characterisation services for at least 40 requests (Q1–Q4)
- A maintained and accessible inventory of available reference services (Q1, internal)
- Harmonised procedures for service request submission, information on sample preparation and shipment and result reporting are in place (Q2, Internal)
- An updated and accessible inventory of SOPs, laboratory protocols and guidance documents is available (Q2, Internal)
- Emerging diagnostic needs are systematically identified and feed into training and guidance activities (Q4, Internal)

Task T3.2 - Provision of reference material for the detection and typing of *Salmonella*, *STEC*, *Listeria*, *Campylobacter* and *Shigella* upon request. **Lead: ISS**

The EURL will provide reference materials upon request to network laboratories, including reference strains, WGS controls, PCR target sequences and other relevant materials for the pathogens in scope. All reference materials will be certified and provided together with appropriate documentation.

ISS will coordinate this task by assessing incoming requests and assigning them to the appropriate consortium partner based on pathogen expertise. Moreover, ISS will maintain an annually updated, pathogen-specific inventory of available reference materials across partner institutes and relevant commercial providers. Harmonised procedures for request submission, expected turnaround times and instructions for safe use and storage will be provided and revised as needed. A secure platform will be used for sharing sequence data (**MS6**).

Requests will be registered and reviewed annually to identify emerging needs and to inform training activities (WP6) and dissemination of guidance (WP2).

Based on the network's need and on the data reported on the European Union One Health annual Zoonoses report, additional reference materials may be produced, when needed.

Expected outcomes

- Network laboratories have access to reference material provision services for at least 20 requests (Q1–Q4)
- A maintained and accessible inventory of reference materials (Q1, Internal)
- Harmonised instructions for safe use and storage of reference materials (Q1, Internal)
- Internal procedure for request registration, setting the plan for feedback, prioritisation, referral and result recording (Q2, Internal)
- Emerging needs related to reference materials inform training and guidance activities (Q4, Internal)

Task T3.3 - Provision of scientific advice and technical support to the network laboratories in relation to *Salmonella*, *STEC*, *Listeria*, *Campylobacter*, *Shigella*, *Vibrio spp.*, *Yersinia spp.* (excluding *Y. pestis*) and other relevant pathogens upon request. **Lead: RIVM**

The EURL will provide scientific advice and technical support upon request to network laboratories on laboratory-related issues for relevant pathogens, including validation data, troubleshooting of methods and result interpretation, guidance on method adoption and quality assurance, molecular epidemiological analyses and, where necessary, on-site support.

RIVM will coordinate this task by assessing incoming requests and assigning them to the appropriate consortium partner based on pathogen expertise. Harmonised procedures for request submission, acknowledgement and handling will be applied. A secure platform will be used for sharing sequence data.

Requests and outcomes will be reviewed annually to identify recurring issues and emerging needs, which will inform training activities (WP6) and dissemination of network-wide guidance (WP2). ECDC will be informed in case of repeated signals indicating broader methodological or surveillance issues.

Expected outcomes

- Network laboratories have access to scientific advice and technical support for at least 15 requests (Q1–Q4)
- Harmonised procedures and instructions for requesting scientific advice and technical support (Q1, internal)
- Internal procedure for request registration, referral and result recording (Q1, internal)
- Recurring technical issues are identified and addressed through training and guidance activities (Q4, internal)

3.4 WORK PACKAGE 4: EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSESSMENT SCHEMES (EQAs)

Task T4.1 - Provision of EQAs. Lead: RIVM

As part of the activities of the EURL-PH-FWDB under WP4, a structured plan will be implemented for the organisation of five EQAs in 2026, each focusing on a key food- and waterborne pathogen of public health relevance: *Campylobacter*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella* and Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC). For each pathogen-specific EQA, the EURL will design, prepare and distribute well-characterised test materials to participating NRLs, accompanied by detailed technical and safety instructions.

The EQAs will evaluate laboratory performance in essential areas, including pathogen identification, phenotypic and/or molecular typing, cluster detection and, where relevant, assessment of virulence markers. The EURL will analyse the submitted results, provide individualised feedback to participating laboratories and compile summary reports highlighting overall performance, methodological strengths and areas for improvement. The outcomes of the EQAs will support continuous capacity building within the EU laboratory network, contribute to harmonisation of analytical approaches and strengthen surveillance of food- and waterborne bacterial diseases across Member States.

To support consistency and comparability across EQAs, the EURL will apply harmonised templates and procedures for EQA implementation, including templates for EQA plans, technical instructions, result submission, expected results reporting, individual feedback, certificates of participation and summary reporting. These templates and procedures will be applied across pathogen-specific EQAs and updated as needed in alignment with the ECDC “Guide for EU-level EQAs for public health microbiology laboratories”.

An overview of the EQA topics and implementation periods planned for 2026 is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of EQAs planned in 2026.

EQA scheme #	Pathogen	Topic	Period
1	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Genotyping & cluster analysis	Spring 2026
2	<i>Salmonella</i>	Serotyping & cluster analysis	Spring 2026
3	STEC	Virulence-gene detection, <i>stx</i> -subtyping, serotyping & cluster analysis	Fall 2026
4	<i>Campylobacter</i>	Species, genotyping & cluster analysis	Fall 2026
5	<i>Shigella</i>	Species, serotyping & cluster analysis	Fall 2026

Description of the EQA timeline

Each EQA follows a structured 12-month cycle. At the start of the cycle, a detailed EQA plan is prepared and submitted (Deliverables **D4.1**, **D4.5**, **D4.9**, **D4.13** and **D4.17**, depending on the EQA), and invitations are sent to prospective NRLs. Following registration of participants, preparation of EQA materials takes place, followed by shipment of materials to participating laboratories.

After distribution of materials, participating laboratories carry out the analyses within the defined timeframe. The EURL subsequently distributes the expected results report (Deliverables **D4.2**, **D4.6**, **D4.10**, **D4.14** and **D4.18**, as applicable). Individual feedback reports and certificates of participation are then provided to each laboratory (Deliverables **D4.3**, **D4.7**, **D4.11**, **D4.15** and **D4.19**). The EQA cycle concludes with submission of a comprehensive summary report describing network performance, methodological observations and recommendations for future EQAs (Deliverables **D4.4**, **D4.8**, **D4.12**, **D4.16** and **D4.20**).

All deliverables generated under this task, covering the different phases of the EQA process before, during and after implementation, will be prepared, agreed with ECDC where required, and submitted in accordance with the requirements and timelines set out in the Grant Agreement, in alignment with the ECDC “Guide for EU-level EQAs for public health microbiology laboratories” and, where appropriate, the ECDC style guide.

The timeline is visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Overview of EQA timeline by month (1-12). Bold text indicates official deliverables (D4.1-4 as an example based on EQA scheme no.1)

Expected outcomes:

- Harmonised EQA templates and procedures are in place to support consistent implementation, evaluation and reporting across pathogen-specific EQAs (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- Participating laboratories receive standardised feedback and certificates of participation to support quality improvement and recognition of participation, with deliverables achieved in Q1–Q4 for spring EQAs and following completion of the EQA cycle for fall EQAs (internal).
- Five EQAs (EQA1-5) covering key food- and waterborne pathogens are implemented to assess laboratory performance across the EU network (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- Participating laboratories receive individual feedback on their performance to support quality improvement and harmonisation of methods, with delivery aligned to the completion of individual EQA cycles (internal).

- EQA results support identification of strengths, gaps and training needs within the network executed in WP6 (Q1–Q4, Internal).
- EQA activities contribute to harmonised laboratory practices and high-quality surveillance of food- and waterborne bacterial diseases (Q1–Q4, Internal).

3.5 WORK PACKAGE 5: SCIENTIFIC ADVICE AND TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE

The scientific advice and technical assistance provided under WP5 will cover pathogens within the scope of the EURL, including *Salmonella* spp., STEC, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* spp., *Shigella* spp., *Vibrio* spp. and *Yersinia* spp. (excluding *Y. pestis*).

Task T5.1 - Participation in ECDC-EFSA Advisory Board meetings. Lead: RIVM

Upon request by ECDC, one EURL representative per pathogen will participate in ECDC–EFSA Advisory Board meetings and provide scientific advice within the scope of the EURL. The advice will relate to the management and sharing of molecular typing data of isolates from human, food, feed, animals and the related environment for public health purposes.

RIVM will coordinate this task and ensure the availability of appropriate EURL representatives per pathogen for participation in the ECDC–EFSA Advisory Board meetings. Information from the meetings, including topics discussed and EURL contributions, will be summarised to support EURL reporting activities.

Expected outcomes:

- EURL representatives per pathogen are available to participate in ECDC–EFSA Advisory Board meetings (Q1–Q4, internal).
- Scientific advice within the scope of the EURL is provided through participation in ECDC–EFSA Advisory Board meetings (Q1–Q4, internal).
- Information from ECDC–EFSA Advisory Board meetings is summarised to support EURL reporting activities (Q4, internal).

Task T5.2 - Scientific advice to ECDC based on expert opinion and/or network survey. Lead: RIVM

Upon request by ECDC, the EURL will provide scientific advice for at least one request per year. The advice may address applicable laboratory methodologies, capacities and capability gaps within the network, or specific aspects of pathogens within the EURL scope. Scientific advice will be based on expert opinion, high-quality scientific evidence and, where relevant, information obtained through network surveys.

RIVM will coordinate this task and ensure that appropriate expertise within the EURL is available. In agreement with ECDC, procedures for handling different types of ECDC requests, including contact points and experts' lists per pathogen, will be established and shared with ECDC. Secure platforms, including the ECDC SharePoint site with access for ECDC and the EURL, will be used for sharing sensitive information when required.

Scientific advice provided under this task will be documented according to GA requirements to support follow-up, coordination and reporting.

Expected outcomes:

- Expertise within the EURL is available to provide scientific advice to ECDC upon request (Q1–Q4, internal).
- ECDC has access to scientific advice for at least one request per year (Q1–Q4, internal).
- Procedures and contact points for each pathogen and areas of expertise are in place to support handling and coordination of ECDC requests (Q1–Q4, internal).
- Scientific advice provided to ECDC is documented to support follow-up and reporting (Q4, internal).

Task T5.3 - *Provide information, guidance and/or support to ECDC in outbreak situations and contribute to ECDC risk assessments.* **Lead: SSI**

In the event of a confirmed multi-country outbreak or other unusual event, the EURL will assist ECDC, upon request, with information, guidance and scientific support. Support will relate to microbiology-relevant aspects of outbreaks, including interpretation of laboratory and surveillance data, and contributions to discussions in EpiPulse platform. Upon request by ECDC, the EURL will also contribute to ECDC risk assessments or to ECDC–EFSA joint outbreak assessments by providing input on pathogen-specific features and appropriate laboratory methodologies, including WGS-based approaches. Support will be provided for at least two requests per year.

The EURL may also contribute to presentations at coordination meetings convened by the European Commission, such as the Health Security Committee or the Advisory Committee on Public Health, and support ECDC and the European Commission on risk communication activities.

Procedures and expert contact points will be in place to support rapid coordination and response to outbreak-related requests.

Support and contributions provided under this task will be documented, including the nature of the request, the support provided and the timing of the response, to support follow-up and progress reporting.

Expected outcomes:

- ECDC has access to EURL support and guidance in outbreak situations for at least two requests (Q1–Q4, internal).
- EURL expertise contributes to ECDC risk assessments or ECDC–EFSA joint outbreak assessments (Q1–Q4, internal).
- ECDC and the European Commission have access to EURL support for risk communication and coordination activities (Q1–Q4, internal).
- EURL expertise is available for outbreak-related information exchange through relevant platforms, including EpiPulse (Q1–Q4, internal).
- Procedures and expert contact points are in place to support rapid coordination of outbreak-related requests (Q1–Q4, internal).
- Support and contributions are documented for follow-up and reporting purposes (Q1–Q4, internal).

3.6 WORK PACKAGE 6: TRAINING

Common approach for Tasks T6.1 and T6.2

The EURL will deliver a coordinated training programme combining in-person trainings and scientific or technical webinars. Both formats are designed to strengthen laboratory capacity and harmonisation across the network by addressing laboratory topics related to *Salmonella* spp., STEC, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* spp. and *Shigella* spp., and, where justified by network needs, extending to *Vibrio* spp., and *Yersinia* spp. (excluding *Y. pestis*).

Training activities will be informed by the methods covered by EQAs, other identified disease network needs, and feedback collected through surveys conducted under WP2. A training needs list will be established, maintained and used to support the planning and prioritisation of training activities.

For each training activity, a training plan will be prepared, agreed with ECDC and submitted to HaDEA in line with the requirements of the Grant Agreement (Deliverables **D6.1**, **D6.2** and **D6.15**).

For all training formats, training agendas and materials will be made available electronically to network laboratories after completion of each activity, and summaries of the conducted trainings (including agendas, participant lists and presentations) will be prepared for inclusion in progress reporting. Participant feedback will be collected and used to inform future training planning and other EURL activities.

Task T6.1 – Organisation and delivery of in-person trainings. Lead: SSI

In 2026, the EURL will organise two in-person training activities for staff from network laboratories. The trainings will focus on topics related to the methods covered by the EQAs and other identified disease network needs.

The first in-person training will be hosted by RIVM (The Netherlands) on 3-4 June and will focus on *Salmonella* serotyping and cluster detection including troubleshooting of common issues identified through typing EQAs executed under ECDC contracts in the past years. The second in-person training will be hosted by ISS (Italy) and delivered in two one-week sessions, on 7–11 September and 14–18 September, each accommodating 10 participants. The training will consist of hands-on laboratory training on RT-PCR for *E. coli* pathogroups identification and characterisation of STEC.

Expected outcomes

- A training needs list is established and maintained to support planning and prioritisation of training activities, informed by training-related questions included in the network survey conducted under WP2 (Q1–Q4, internal)
- Network laboratories have access to two in-person training activities in 2026, each involving at least 20 participants (Q1–Q4)

- Training materials are accessible to network laboratories after completion of each training activity (Q4, internal)
- Summaries of conducted trainings, including training agendas, participant lists and presentations, are prepared for inclusion in progress reporting (Q4, internal)
- Participant feedback is collected and contributes to the evaluation and planning of future training activities (Q4, internal)

Task T6.2 – Organisation and delivery of scientific or technical webinars. Lead: SSI

In 2026, the EURL will organise one scientific or technical webinar focusing on laboratory topics relevant to the scope of the EURL and identified disease network needs.

The webinar will be delivered online and made accessible to all network laboratory members. To ensure broad accessibility and reach, the ECDC Learning Portal will be used where appropriate.

Expected outcomes

- Network laboratories have access to at least one scientific or technical webinar in 2026 addressing laboratory topics within the scope of the EURL (Q1–Q4)
- Webinar materials are accessible to network laboratories after completion of the activity and made available through the ECDC SharePoint platform and, where applicable, the ECDC Learning Portal (Q4, internal)
- Summaries of the conducted webinar, including the agenda, participant list and presentations, are prepared for inclusion in progress reporting (Q4, internal)
- Participant feedback is collected and contributes to the evaluation and planning of future training and capacity-building activities (Q4, internal)

Table 1: Contractual deliverables scheduled for Year 1 (2026) of EURL-PH-FWDB, in accordance with the Grant Agreement

WP	Task	DL No	DL Name	Lead	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date
WP1	T1.1	D1.1*	Work plan – Year 1	SSI	Document, Report	Public	M2
WP1	T1.1	D1.2*	Work plan – Year 2	SSI	Document, Report	Public	M10
WP1	T1.2	D1.8*	Meeting agendas for laboratory members of the disease network – Year 1	SSI	Document, Report	Public	M11
WP1	T1.2	D1.15*	Network meeting report – Year 1	SSI	Document, Report	Sensitive	M14**
WP2	T2.1	D2.1	Project leaflet	SSI	Document, Report	Public	M6
WP2	T2.1	D2.2	EURL-PH-FWDB website	SSI	DEC – Websites, etc.	Public	M6
WP2	T2.1	D2.3	Communication and dissemination plan	SSI	Document, Report	Public	M6
WP4	T4.1	D4.1*	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 1: A detailed plan	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M8
WP4	T4.1	D4.2	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No. 1: Summary of sample composition and expected results	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M15**
WP4	T4.1	D4.3	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No. 1: Individual participant feedback reports	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M18**
WP4	T4.1	D4.5*	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 2: A detailed plan	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M8
WP4	T4.1	D4.6	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No. 2: Summary of sample composition and expected results	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M15**
WP4	T4.1	D4.7	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No. 2: Individual participant feedback reports	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M18**
WP4	T4.1	D4.9*	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 3: A detailed plan	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M8
WP4	T4.1	D4.10	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No. 3: Summary of sample composition and expected results	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M15**
WP4	T4.1	D4.13*	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 4: A detailed plan	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M8
WP4	T4.1	D4.14	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No. 4: Summary of sample	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M15**

			composition and expected results				
WP4	T4.1	D4.17*	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 5: A detailed plan	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M8
WP4	T4.1	D4.18	EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No. 5: Summary of sample composition and expected results	RIVM	Document, Report	Sensitive	M15**
WP6	T6.1	D6.1*	A training plan for in-person training 1 – Year 1	SSI	Public	Public	M10
WP6	T6.1	D6.2*	A training plan for in-person training 2 – Year 1	SSI	Public	Public	M10
WP6	T6.2	D6.15*	A training plan for scientific or technical webinar – Year 1	SSI	Public	Public	M10

**Deliverables that will be agreed with ECDC before their submission to HaDEA*

***Deliverable that contractually have a deadline in Year 2, but will be submitted in Year 1 (see Fig. 2 for expected submission dates)*

Table 2: Project milestones scheduled in year 1 (2026) of EURL-PH-FWDB

WP	Task	MS No	MS Name	Lead	Means of Verification	Due Date
WP1	T1.1	MS1	Collection of network laboratory contact lists	SSI	Contact lists of network laboratories compiled	M2
WP1	T1.1	MS2	EURL-PH-FWDB kick-off meeting (in-person + online part)	SSI	Meeting held and minutes/presentations circulated to participants	M2
WP1	T1.1	MS3	Info meeting for the network laboratories (online)	SSI	Meeting held and minutes/presentations circulated to participants	M3
WP1	T1.3	MS4	Establishing contact with relevant EURLs and other initiatives	SSI	Contact lists of relevant EURLs and other initiatives compiled	M6
WP2	T2.2	MS5	Setting up and updating EURL mailbox	SSI	EURL mailbox(es) set	M6
WP2	T2.2	MS6	Development of secure share platform(s) for sharing large files	SSI	Secure share platform(s) set and accessible	M6
WP2	T2.3	MS7	Survey to identify national laboratories' services and needs for support in the network laboratories	SSI	Survey results summarised in annual progress/periodic report	M10

Gantt chart

WP	Task	Deliverable/Milestone/Activity	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	
WP1	T1.1	Coordination of activities with network laboratories and ECDC													
		Work plans – Year 1 and Year 2			D1.1								D1.2		
		Collection of network laboratory contact lists			MS1										
		EURL-PH-FWDB kick-off meeting			MS2										
		Info meeting for the network laboratories (online)				MS3									
WP1	T1.2	Organisation of network meetings for network laboratories													
		Meeting agendas for laboratory members of the disease network – Year 1											D1.8		
		Network meeting report – Year 1												D1.15	
WP1	T1.3	Coordination with other EURLs or relevant initiatives													
		Establishing contact with relevant EURLs and other initiatives							MS4						
WP2	T2.1	Continuous communication with the network laboratories and relevant stakeholders													
		Project leaflet							D2.1						
		EURL-PH-FWDB Website								D2.2					
		Communication and dissemination plan								D2.3					
WP2	T2.2	Continuous dissemination of EURL output of support activities to the network laboratories and relevant stakeholders													
		Setting up and updating EURL mailbox								MS5					
		Development of secure share platform(s) for sharing large files									MS6				
WP2	T2.3	Evaluation of EURL activities													
		Survey to identify national laboratories' services and needs for support in the network laboratories												MS7	
WP4	T4.1	Provision of EQAs													
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 1: A detailed plan							D4.1						
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 1: Expected results report											D4.2		
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 1: Individual participant feedback report												D4.3	
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 2: A detailed plan							D4.5						
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 2: Expected results report											D4.6		
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 2: Individual participant feedback report												D4.7	
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 3: A detailed plan									D4.9				
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 3: Expected results report												D4.10	
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 4: A detailed plan									D4.13				
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 4: Expected results report												D4.14	
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 5: A detailed plan									D4.17				
		EURL-PH-FWDB EQA Scheme No 5: Expected results report											D4.18		
WP6	T6.1	Organisation and delivery of in-person trainings													
		A training plan for in-person training 1 – Year 1				D6.1									
		A training plan for in-person training 2 – Year 1				D6.2									
WP6	T6.2	Organization and delivery of scientific or technical webinars													
		A training plan for scientific or technical webinar – Year 1											D6.15		

Color codes:

MSX	Milestone submission date to HaDEA
DX.X	Deliverable submission date to HaDEA

Figure 2: The Gantt chart reflects the planned timing of activities and expected submission of outputs for EURL-PH-FWDB. Contractual deadlines for deliverables and milestones are reported in Table 1 and Table 2. The colours for Tasks indicate the leading institute: grey – SSI, orange – RIVM. No deliverables and milestones are planned for tasks within the WP3 and WP5, led by ISS and RIVM, respectively.

4 PROGRESS REPORTING

Progress on annual activities and achievements will be reported in annual Progress Reports submitted one month after the end of the reporting year. The first Progress Report for Year 1 (2026) is due in M13.

Progress reporting will follow the action-level reporting requirements defined in the call text EU4H-2024-DGA-MS-IBA-03 and will cover all activities and outputs implemented under the work packages in the reporting year. Reporting will include as applicable, structured information on coordination and networking activities, communication and dissemination actions, reference services and scientific support provided to network laboratories, scientific advice and outbreak-related support to ECDC, and capacity-building activities such as trainings and webinars.

For each task, reporting will include brief descriptions of activities performed, relevant timelines,

involved participants and EURL partners, and references to outputs produced where applicable. Detailed task-specific reporting elements aligned with the call requirements will be applied internally to ensure consistent, complete, and compliant reporting across work packages.

5 DOCUMENT REVIEW / APPROVAL (THE COORDINATOR)

Name	Role	Action (review / approval)	Date
David Canovas Jorda	Project officer (HaDEA)	approval	2/03/2026